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Inprodat e.V. Gender Equality Plan

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1 Introduction

The Innovation Centre for Process Data Technology, Inprodat e.V., is a public-benefit *non-governmental organization* (NGO) in Rhineland-Palatinate, Germany. Inprodat e.V. may potentially also qualify for the status of a *research organization* (RO) following the EC’s legal entity rules [1]. Within the EU’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, it is mandatory for ROs to adhere to EC guidance [2] and publish an institutional gender equality plan (GEP).

This is the GEP of Inprodat e.V., compiled and published in compliance with the EC’s specifications [2]. Inprodat e.V. will support the EC’s strategy for a *Union of Equality* [3]: “Working together, we can **make real progress by 2025** in achieving a Europe where women and men, girls and boys, in all their diversity, are equal – where they are free to pursue their chosen path in life and reach their full potential, where they have equal opportunities to thrive, and where they can equally participate in and lead our European society” [3].

2 Four mandatory process-related requirements

2.1 Public document

Inprodat’s GEP can be accessed through doi:10.5281/zenodo.5524638; relying on a functionality from Zenodo, this DOI will continue to point to the most recent version of this document approved by the association. **The GEP will be revised yearly**, subject to approval by the Annual General Meeting.

2.2 Dedicated resources

Inprodat commits **15% of the indirect cost (overhead) from all EC funding**, notably within the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, to gender-equality related expenses within the remit of the organization following § 2 of the Inprodat e.V. statutes and § 52 of the German *Abgabenordnung* (AO).

Inprodat has formed a **gender equality committee (GEC)** with the tasks of *a)* overseeing implementation and compliance with the GEP, *b)* preparing its yearly updates, including data collection and monitoring, and *c)* advising on the use of the dedicated EC funding overhead fraction specified above in compliance with § 7 of the Inprodat e.V. statutes.

From 5th May 2022, the members of the GEC are Silvia Chiacchiera, Gabriela Guevara Carrión, and Heinz A. Preisig.

2.3 Data collection and monitoring

According to EC guidance [2], “organisations must collect sex/gender disaggregated data on personnel (and students, for the establishments concerned)”.

As of 5th May 2022, Inprodat e.V. employs zero staff (thereof, 0 of any gender). It is involved in teaching zero students (thereof, 0 of any gender). Subsequent to the 2022 Inprodat AGM, there is one woman among the three members of the managing board (**33%**), and there are three women among the eight members of the extended board (**38%**). Out of the 15 members of the association, four are women (**27%**). Inprodat e.V. has not yet officially organized or co-organized any academic events such as conferences or workshops for which the fraction of female committee members, invited speakers, contributors, and attendees could be evaluated. The KPIs above will be tracked over time to **monitor organizational progress**.

The GEC will continue to collect and publish these data over time; they will be reported in the future versions of the GEP. We will thus “ensure that data is **published and monitored on an annual basis**” [2]. If the development indicates that in order to *make real progress by 2025*, corrective measures are needed, such measures will be developed and introduced in due course.

2.4 Training

Inprodat e.V. engages in continuous professional development, involving all members, where the GEC will have a leading role and ensure that gender aspects will be taken into account. All training materials to be developed by Inprodat e.V. will be evaluated for gender aspects. Where gender aspects should be addressed, following GEC advice, that will be done. The training materials will be made accessible to members and the community at large. Academic events organized or co-organized by Inprodat will be monitored for the KPIs mentioned above (fraction of women among the committee members, the invited speakers, the contributors, and the attendees).

As soon as the activities of the association reach a sufficient level, training materials specifically dedicated to gender equality and the gender aspects of disciplinary topics will be developed; similarly, dedicated training events or parts of events will be organized. For this purpose, the organization will be following GEC advice, expending the dedicated resources mentioned above.

Endorsement. The present version has been approved by the Inprodat e.V. annual general meeting held on 5th May 2022.

References

- [1] EC: 2022, ‘Rules for Legal Entity Validation, LEAR Appointment and Financial Capacity Assessment, version 4.0’. Technical report, EC.
- [2] M. STAREVA and A. PÉPIN (eds.): 2021, *Horizon Europe Guidance on Gender Equality Plans*. Luxembourg: EU Publication Office. ISBN 978-92-76-39184-5, doi:10.2777/876509.
- [3] EC: 2020, ‘A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025’. Technical Report COM(2020) 152 final, EC.